

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

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Deliverable D5.2:

UNITI's In-Silico Model and DSS

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1 Introduction

The UNITI project involves a large-scale randomized controlled trial (RCT) with extensive data collection, which is used to develop a Clinical Decision Support System (DSS, figure 1) with two cores. The DSS is designed to recommend tailored examinations and optimal treatment strategies for individual tinnitus patients based on their profiles. The RCT dataset includes a comprehensive set of questionnaires, audiological measurements, genetic data and biomarker information that provide a diverse and robust foundation for the development of the DSS. The deliverable will report on the UNITI in-silico model and DSS developed by the UNITI partner ICCS (Athens) as well as an additional DSS developed by the UNITI partner OVGU (Magdeburg).

Since all clinicians interface with the patient data using the Tinnitus Database, the DSS outputs are integrated into the Tinnitus Database user interface, along with additional visualizations and information regarding the data and questionnaires collected so far. It is expected that the clinician can have an overview of not just the patients' symptoms and tinnitus characteristics, but also get the degree to which a patient would improve given each of the treatment and treatment combinations explored in the UNITI RCT.

UNITI Decision Support System		
<small>Predicted values are total THI scores after 12 weeks of treatment. Confidence Intervals (CI) are given for Core #2. For more information click help (?). This DSS was developed by the UNITI project, which received funding from the EU (GA Nr. 848261).</small>		
TREATMENT	CORE #1 THI PRED.	CORE #2 THI PRED.
Hearing Aids	22	26 [CI: 24-44]
Hearing Aids and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy	23	32 [CI: 25-42]
Hearing Aids and Structured Counselling	25	35 [CI: 18-50]
Hearing Aids and Sound Therapy	26	31 [CI: 23-52]
Sound Therapy	28	38 [CI: 22-59]
Structured Counselling	29	43 [CI: 15-55]
Cognitive Behavioral Therapy	31	39 [CI: 27-39]
Structured Counselling and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy	32	42 [CI: 21-47]
Sound Therapy and Structured Counselling	33	41 [CI: 18-57]
Sound Therapy and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy	35	38 [CI: 24-49]

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Decision Support System. The figure shows the output of a the DSS for a randomly selected patient. The patient presented at baseline with a THI value of 46. According to the prediction of DSS Core1 it can be expected that the treatment with hearing aids leads to the largest improvement with a THI value of 22 after 12 weeks. According to the DSS Core2, it can also be expected that hearing aids lead to the best treatment outcome - with a THI value of 26.

The two cores comprising the DSS are developed with complementary goals: The DSS core described in **Section 2** builds a predictor for treatment improvement given the data collected in the UNITI and optimizes for predictive performance, while the design of the DSS in **Section 3** is inspired by the findings from the analysis of the historical center-level data, and also prioritizes the ranking of treatments in order of applicability to a patient in addition to optimizing

for predictive performance. It was also found that supporting missing values during generation of predictions helps generate predictions for patients for whom data collection is still in progress (i.e., results from an audiological exam might not yet have come in) – which is closer to the use case in a live environment. Validations of both cores are provided in the respective section.

2 Overview of the UNITI Decision Support System (DSS Core 1) from ICCS

Personalized healthcare has revolutionized how we address medical conditions. Tinnitus management is no exception. Rather than adopting a one-size-fits-all approach, our DSS seeks to provide tailored recommendations for interventions, thereby enhancing the efficacy of treatment and the well-being of tinnitus patients.

Objectives

Personalized Intervention: Our primary goal is to create a DSS¹ capable of predicting the most effective interventions for tinnitus management. These interventions encompass Hearing Aids (HA), Sound Therapy (ST), Structured Counseling (SC), Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), and various combinations thereof. In total, we have defined ten unique intervention strategies.

Quality of Life Improvement: Beyond clinical outcomes, we aim to improve the overall quality of life for tinnitus patients. Our DSS recommendations go beyond mere symptom management to address holistic well-being.

Clinical Decision Support: We intend for healthcare professionals to use our DSS as a valuable tool in their decision-making process. By providing evidence-based recommendations, our DSS assists medical practitioners in delivering the best possible care to tinnitus patients.

Our DSS covers an extensive range of interventions, spanning the following ten possibilities:

Figure 2. Single or combinational types of interventions (HA=Hearing Aid, CBT=Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, ST=Sound Therapy, SC=Structured Counselling).

These interventions form the cornerstone of our tinnitus management approach. The DSS is designed to cater to both patients seeking self-guided management and healthcare professionals seeking data-driven clinical decision support.

2.1 Data Handling

2.1.1 Data Collection

Our data collection process involved the systematic collection of patient data from the baseline assessments. These assessments included a wide array of patient characteristics, responses to questionnaires, detailed audiometric readings, extensive psychological assessments and nuanced responses to health-related questionnaires. Of particular significance was the collection of the target variable—the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) score obtained during the final visit.

The Python script we've developed for this purpose not only fetches this data but also ensures that it is formatted and structured in a manner conducive to advanced analytical processing. This seamless integration of database management and data analysis is pivotal to the functionality of our DSS.

Figure 3. No. of overall features: 282. ESIT-SQ=*The European School for Interdisciplinary Tinnitus Research Screening Questionnaire*; Mini-SOISES=*short version of the Social Isolation Electronic Survey*; FTQ=*Fear of Tinnitus Questionnaire*; WHOQOL-BREF= *World Health Organization Quality of Life BREF*; Mini-TQ=*short form of the Tinnitus Questionnaire*; THI=*Tinnitus Handicap Inventory*; GUEF=*Questionnaire on Hypersensitivity to Sound*; PHQ-9=*Patient Health Questionnaire 9*; BFI-2=*Big Five Inventory-2*; TFI=*Tinnitus Functional Index*.

2.1.2 Data Preprocessing

2.1.2.1 Data Cleaning and Normalization

Sophisticated Handling of Missing Values: In our approach to managing missing data, we've employed multiple imputation techniques. Depending on the dataset and the nature of the missing values, we utilize methods ranging from mean or median imputation for simpler cases to more complex approaches. For example, we have employed K-nearest neighbors (KNN) imputation for more nuanced handling of missing values, ensuring that the imputed values are reasonable approximations of the missing data.

Advanced Normalization Techniques: We standardize the range of independent variables through Z-score normalization, which adjusts the data to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one.

2.1.2.2 Handling Outliers

In the UNITI Decision Support System, we place a strong emphasis on ensuring the accuracy and integrity of our data, which is crucial for making reliable and effective treatment recommendations. A key aspect of this process is the identification and handling of outliers—data points that deviate significantly from the rest of the dataset. Outliers can potentially skew our analysis, leading to inaccurate conclusions.

Our Approach to Outlier Detection

Categorization Based on Expected Ranges: We start by categorizing the data based on their expected value ranges. For example, some responses from our questionnaires are expected to fall within specific numerical ranges. By identifying these expected ranges for different types of data, we can more accurately pinpoint which values are likely to be outliers.

Systematic Checking Against Ranges: Using these predefined ranges, we systematically review our data. This process involves comparing the actual values in our dataset against their expected ranges. If a value falls outside its expected range, it is flagged as an outlier.

Handling Outliers

Treatment of Outliers: Once identified, outliers are treated with care to ensure they do not negatively impact our analysis. In some cases, we might adjust these values to bring them within a more reasonable range, or in certain situations, we may exclude them from the analysis. This decision is made based on the nature of the data and the potential impact of the outlier.

Context-Specific Considerations: In the UNITI Decision Support System, we take special care in handling data that are particularly sensitive or critical to our analysis. For instance, consider the case where we collect data on patients' physical characteristics, such as height and weight. These measurements are vital as they can significantly influence the choice and effectiveness of certain tinnitus treatments.

Physical Characteristics (e.g., Height and Weight):

Identification: During our outlier detection process, we might find that a patient's reported height is exceptionally high or low, falling well outside the typical range for adult heights. For example, a height of 280 cm (approximately 9 feet) would be extremely rare and likely an error or an outlier.

Treatment: In such cases, instead of automatically excluding this data point, we first consider the possibility of data entry errors or other reasonable explanations. If an error is suspected, we may reach out for clarification or adjust the value based on additional information. If the value is confirmed to be accurate but highly unusual, we may decide to handle it separately to avoid skewing our overall analysis.

Advanced Outlier Detection in THI Score Analysis

In addition to our standard outlier detection methods, the UNITI Decision Support System employs a specialized approach for analyzing outliers in the context of Tinnitus Handicap

Inventory (THI) score changes. This is particularly important as THI scores are a key metric in assessing the severity and impact of tinnitus on patients.

THI Score Difference Analysis

Calculation of THI Score Differences: We calculate the difference in THI scores over time (labelled as THI_diff). This is done by subtracting the final THI score (post-treatment or at a follow-up stage) from the baseline THI score (pre-treatment). The difference in these scores is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of the interventions.

Outlier Treatment in THI Score Differences

Interquartile Range (IQR) for Outlier Detection: We employ the Interquartile Range (IQR) method to identify potential outliers in the THI score differences. By calculating the IQR and setting thresholds (1.5 times the IQR above the third quartile and below the first quartile), we can pinpoint score changes that are unusually high or low.

Refinement of Data: Data points identified as outliers are carefully examined and excluded from our analysis if they fall outside these IQR thresholds. This step ensures that our analysis of treatment effectiveness is based on data that accurately represent typical patient responses.

Resetting the Dataset: After addressing outliers, we reset our datasets, ensuring they are streamlined and focused only on relevant and representative data. This process is applied to both our training and test datasets to maintain consistency and reliability in our analysis.

Impact on Treatment Analysis

Enhanced Understanding of Treatment Efficacy: By meticulously analyzing and treating outliers in THI score differences, we gain a more accurate understanding of how different intervention protocols affect patients. This approach allows us to draw more reliable conclusions about the effectiveness of various tinnitus treatments.

Accurate outlier detection and treatment form the foundation for the reliable predictions and recommendations our system makes. By ensuring the data we use is of the highest quality, we can confidently provide healthcare professionals and patients with insights that truly reflect individual patient needs and conditions.

2.1.2.3 Feature Engineering

Innovative Creation of New Features: We have created numerous new features to capture the complexities of the data. This includes the generation of interaction terms to explore the combined effect of two or more variables, and the development of composite indices that aggregate information from multiple related variables into a single, more powerful predictor.

Advanced Transformations of Variables: We employ a range of transformations to enhance the predictive power of our variables. For example, polynomial transformations are used to capture non-linear relationships, and principal component analysis (PCA) is applied to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset while retaining the most informative aspects of the data.

2.1.2.4 Integration and Analysis of Audiological Data in the UNITI DSS

In the UNITI Decision Support System, a crucial component of our data analysis involves the meticulous handling and integration of audiological data. Audiology, being a critical aspect of tinnitus evaluation and treatment, requires careful consideration in how we process and analyze this data. Our approach is designed to ensure the data's accuracy, relevance, and completeness.

Merging of Datasets: We start by merging our audiological dataset with baseline features. This integration is pivotal, as it allows us to maintain a focus on relevant patients, ensuring that our analyses are based on comprehensive and relevant data.

Data Cleaning and Preprocessing:

Handling Missing Values: Our process involves identifying and addressing missing values in key audiological measures. For example, specific frequency loss columns with a large number of missing values are excluded to enhance the dataset's quality.

Standardizing Data Entries: We replace certain placeholder values (like 999 and 888) in frequency loss columns with NaN (Not a Number) to standardize our dataset. This step is crucial in preparing the data for analysis, ensuring consistency and accuracy.

Refining Auditory Measures:

Frequency and Loudness Matching: We compute specific auditory measures like the maximum matching frequency and matching loudness for each ear, considering different tinnitus conditions (right, left, or both ears). This computation helps us understand the severity and characteristics of tinnitus on an individual level.

Minimal Masking Levels: Similarly, we process minimal masking levels, another crucial aspect in tinnitus evaluation, to ensure that our dataset accurately reflects the auditory profile of each patient.

Data-Driven Insights

Customized Patient Profiles: By meticulously processing this audiological data, we create detailed patient profiles that are crucial for tailoring treatment recommendations. This level of detail allows us to understand the unique auditory characteristics of each patient's tinnitus.

Impact on Treatment Strategies: The insights derived from this audiological analysis directly influence our treatment strategies. By understanding the nuances of each patient's auditory data, we can better match them with the most effective interventions, enhancing the overall effectiveness of our tinnitus management recommendations.

2.1.2.5 Handling Missing Values – Data Imputation

In the UNITI Decision Support System, we recognize the importance of addressing missing data to ensure the accuracy and reliability of our analyses. Missing data can arise for various reasons, such as non-responses in surveys or gaps in clinical records. To tackle this, we

employ a sophisticated data imputation strategy, which is key to maintaining the integrity of our dataset.

Imputation Methodology

Utilization of Advanced Imputation Techniques: We use advanced imputation methods to fill in missing values in our dataset. This approach ensures that we retain as much valuable information as possible, enhancing the quality of our data.

KNN Imputer Implementation

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Imputation: We utilize the KNN Imputation method, which estimates missing values based on similar data points. By considering 'n_neighbors'—the number of nearest neighbors to each data point—we ensure that the imputed values are reasonable approximations based on similar cases in our dataset.

Application to Training and Test Sets: This imputation is applied to both our training set (X_train) and our test set (X_test). We create a new data frame with the imputed values, maintaining the original structure and indexes of our datasets.

Refinement of Imputation Strategy: We explore different configurations for the number of neighbors in the KNN Imputer (such as 3, 5, 7, 9 neighbors) to determine the optimal approach for our data. This fine-tuning is crucial in ensuring that the imputed values align closely with the true nature of the data.

Enhanced Data Integrity: By carefully addressing missing data, we significantly improve the reliability of our dataset. This step is fundamental in ensuring that our analyses and subsequent recommendations are based on complete and accurate information.

2.1.2.6 Feature Selection

In developing the predictive capabilities of the UNITI Decision Support System, selecting the most informative features is of paramount importance. This process, known as feature selection, involves identifying the data attributes that are most predictive of patient outcomes and are essential for the most accurate model training.

Our Feature Selection Approach

Iterative Refinement: We conducted an iterative process to identify the optimal number of features that contribute to the accuracy of our models. By evaluating a range of feature sets, we determined that a subset of 17 features provides the most accurate predictions.

Selection Criteria: The criteria for selecting these features included their statistical significance, relevance to tinnitus symptoms and treatment outcomes, and their ability to improve model performance.

Resulting Feature Set: The selected features encompass a broad range of data points, from audiological measurements such as hearing loss at specific frequencies and loudness matching levels to questionnaire-derived data like height and weight. Additionally, scores from

the Tinnitus Functional Index and the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory, which provide insight into the functional and emotional impacts of tinnitus on patients, were included.

Significance of Selected Features

Comprehensive Patient Profile: The features we chose paint a comprehensive picture of the patient's condition, considering both clinical audiological data and self-reported measures that reflect the individual's daily experiences and psychological state.

Tailored Treatment Recommendations: These features are crucial in tailoring treatment recommendations. For example, understanding the specific hearing loss profile and the severity of tinnitus as reflected in standardized questionnaires allows the DSS to suggest interventions that are most likely to be effective for each individual patient.

By focusing on a refined set of features, our models are better equipped to learn from the data without being overwhelmed by noise or irrelevant information. This results in more reliable and interpretable models.

2.2 Model training and validation

2.2.1 Model Selection

After careful evaluation of various regression models including Lasso, Ridge and Random Forests (see table 1), the Elastic Net regression model emerged as the most suitable choice due to its capability to handle multicollinearity. Elastic Net combines the penalties of Lasso and Ridge regression, making it particularly useful when there are many correlated features, as it can include all of them in the model but distribute the coefficient estimations among them. It exhibited a remarkable R-squared (R²) score of 0.74 and a commendable Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 9.99 when evaluated on the validation dataset. These metrics underscore the model's capacity to account for a substantial portion of the variance in THI scores.

Table 1: Model comparison

	Elastic Net	L2 Regularization	L1 Regularization	Random Forest
R2 Score	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.69
MSE	9.99	10.10	10.18	10.81

The RMSE of 3.00 for the Elastic Net model highlights its precision in predicting THI scores, suggesting that the model's predictions are on average within three points of the actual scores. This level of accuracy indicates the model's efficacy in estimating the severity of tinnitus symptoms experienced by patients.

2.2.2 Training

1. **Data Splitting:** The dataset, after preprocessing, consisted of 460 patients. However, after applying the preprocessing steps mentioned above, 280 samples were used for training

and validation. It's essential to split the data into training and validation sets to ensure that the model is evaluated on unseen data.

2. **Model Configuration:** The Elastic Net model requires the selection of two hyperparameters:

- α : Represents a mix between Ridge ($\alpha=0$) and Lasso ($\alpha=1$).
- λ or l1ratio: Regularization strength. The larger the value, the more prominent the penalties on the coefficients, pushing more of them towards zero.

Hyperparameter tuning, through cross-validation, have been performed to find the optimal values for these parameters.

3. **Model Training:** With the chosen hyperparameters, the model was trained on the training dataset. The features selected by RFE played a crucial role in the training phase, ensuring that only relevant information was used to make predictions.

2.2.3 Validation

Validation Dataset

To evaluate the performance of the DSS, we employed a common validation technique known as hold-out validation. In this approach, a portion of the dataset was held back and not used during the model training phase. Instead, it served as an independent dataset for validation. Specifically, 25% of the dataset was reserved for this purpose.

Stratification for Representativeness

One key aspect of the validation strategy was the use of stratification. This means that when splitting the data into training and validation sets, we ensured that both sets maintained the same proportion of different interventions (HA, ST, SC, CBT, combinations, etc.) as the original dataset. Stratification helps ensure that the validation set is representative of the diversity of interventions present in the data.

Objective Assessment

The primary objective of this hold-out validation was to objectively assess how well the DSS generalized to unseen data. By separating a portion of the data for validation, we aimed to simulate how the model(s) would perform when making predictions for new patients who were not part of the training dataset.

Performance Metrics

The DSS's performance was evaluated using two key metrics:

R-squared (R²) Score: This metric measures the proportion of the variance in the target variable (THI scores) that is predictable from the independent variables (features). An R² score of 0.74 indicated that the DSS could explain 74% of the variance in THI scores, which suggests a strong predictive capability (see figure 4).

Mean Squared Error (MSE): MSE quantifies the average squared difference between the predicted THI scores and the actual THI scores. With a low MSE of 9.99, the DSS demonstrated high accuracy, implying that its predictions closely matched the true THI scores on average.

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): The RMSE, with a low value of 3, indicates that the DSS achieved highly accurate predictions for the THI score, with small deviations from the true scores, highlighting its effectiveness in estimating tinnitus severity.

Figure 4. Plot representing the closeness between predicted and actual THI scores.

Importance of Hold-Out Validation

Hold-out validation is a widely accepted method in machine learning and predictive modeling. It provides an essential benchmark for assessing how well the model performs on unseen data, helping gauge its real-world applicability.

While cross-validation is another valuable validation technique, the choice of hold-out validation, coupled with stratification, was suitable for the dataset. It allowed us to assess model performance with a clear distinction between the training and validation datasets, and the use of stratification ensured that the validation dataset remained representative of the diversity of interventions in the study.

Overall, this validation strategy provided valuable insights into the DSS's predictive power and generalization capabilities, which are critical for its practical application in personalized tinnitus management.

2.2.4 Confidence Intervals and Model Consistency

2.2.4.1 The Role of Confidence Intervals in Predictive Modeling

Confidence Intervals (CIs) are a pivotal statistical tool in predictive modeling, providing a range within which the true value of an estimated parameter is likely to fall. In the context of our Elastic Net regression model, each THI (Tinnitus Handicap Inventory) score prediction is accompanied by a 95% CI. This interval conveys that there is a 95% probability the true THI score lies within this range. By quantifying the uncertainty inherent in predictions, CIs offer a nuanced view of the model's reliability and precision.

2.2.4.2 Model Performance and Precision

The performance of our model is judiciously assessed by examining the CIs of the predicted THI scores. These intervals are instrumental in evaluating the model's precision. A narrower CI indicates a higher level of precision in prediction, while a wider CI suggests greater uncertainty. For our model, a consistently narrower width of the CIs across various predictions is observed (see figure 5) – for example, a set of features provided a THI score prediction within an approximate range of 57.49 to 58.99.

Figure 5. Predicted THI scores with Confidence Intervals

This uniformity in the narrowness of the CIs across different predictions is a strong indicator of the model's consistency. Unlike models that show significant variability in the size of their CIs, our model demonstrates a commendable level of steadiness. This consistency in the width of the CIs reflects the model's robustness in making precise predictions across a diverse range of patient profiles.

2.2.4.3 Interpretation and Clinical Implications

The consistently narrow CIs observed in our model's predictions are indicative of a reliable predictive performance. In a clinical context, this translates to a high degree of confidence in the THI score predictions made by the model, which is essential for informed decision-making. Clinicians can use these predictions, bolstered by the assurance of narrow CIs, to discuss potential treatment outcomes and strategies with patients.

2.2.5 Additional External Validation

In addition to the validation process we conducted above, we sought to fortify the validation of our model with a supplementary dataset procured from external sources. Our clinical partners graciously facilitated this process by providing fully anonymized data from their respective clinics. This additional dataset comprised data from 37 patients, serving as a robust basis for our external validation efforts.

The acquisition of this data from the same clinical environments that contributed to the UNITI project database is particularly advantageous. It ensures consistency in the data collection methodologies, the diagnostic tools employed, and adherence to the established protocols. Such uniformity is crucial as it minimizes variability in data quality and patient management approaches, thereby enhancing the reliability of our validation process.

We subjected this newly acquired dataset to a rigorous validation process, applying the same analytical models that had been previously utilized within the UNITI project. The model's performance (Elastic Net) on this external dataset was encouraging, with an R-squared (R²) score of 0.72 (see Table 2). This result is closely aligned with our prior validation efforts, indicating a strong and consistent predictive capability of our model.

The validation exercise with the external dataset has been highly affirming. The model's performance, as reflected by the R² score, substantiates its consistency and reinforces our confidence in its generalizability. This consistency across different datasets underscores the robustness of our model and its potential for widespread clinical application in personalized tinnitus management.

Table 1. Model evaluation on external dataset

<i>Metrics</i>	<i>Elastic Net</i>
R ² Score	0.72
MSE	10.10
RMSE	3.19

2.3 Implementation of the Decision Support System

2.3.1 Integration into Clinical Workflow

The Decision Support System (DSS) embedded within tinnitus-database.eu represents a significant stride toward personalized tinnitus care. Its seamless integration into the clinical

workflow allows for real-time analysis and insights, thereby empowering healthcare providers with actionable data at the point of care.

When a patient profile is accessed, the DSS instantaneously retrieves and synthesizes the patient's historical and current clinical data. This integration ensures that healthcare professionals are equipped with up-to-date information, facilitating a dynamic treatment planning process that is responsive to each patient's unique journey.

2.3.2 Personalized Treatment Predictions

At the core of the DSS is the Elastic Net regression model, trained with rigorously curated data to predict treatment outcomes with high precision. This model accounts for the multifaceted nature of tinnitus by considering a wide array of variables from patient demographics to clinical assessments. For patients indicated for Hearing Aid (HA) use, the DSS extends its predictive capability to include a broad range of ten treatment options (see figure 1). This function underscores the DSS's commitment to offering comprehensive care plans that acknowledge the complexity of tinnitus management.

2.3.3 Data Preprocessing and Analysis

The DSS's robust backend functions perform meticulous data preprocessing. This includes validation checks, outlier detection, and normalization of data, ensuring that the model's inputs are of the highest quality. Such preprocessing is crucial in maintaining the integrity of the model's predictions and, by extension, the trust of the clinicians who rely on the system.

2.3.4 User Experience and Interface Design

The user interface (UI) of the DSS has been designed with the end-user in mind. Navigating the system is intuitive, making it accessible to users with varying degrees of technical expertise. Visual elements like graphs and tables are employed to convey complex data in a digestible format, allowing for quick interpretation and decision-making. The UI's design also ensures that predictions and recommendations are presented clearly, fostering an environment for informed patient-provider discussions.

2.3.5 Impact on Patient Care

The DSS does not merely predict treatment outcomes; it embodies a shift toward a more personalized and data-driven approach to healthcare. It enables clinicians to navigate the intricacies of tinnitus management with confidence, offering personalized treatment plans tailored to individual patient needs and preferences.

3 Overview of Core 2 of the UNITI Decision Support System (DSS Core 2) from OVGU

The development of the DSS Core 2 by OVGU was based on methods and insights from WP3 and WP4, mainly methods and insights for phenotyping and prediction with missing questionnaires ¹, and for learning from timestamped mHealth data with high degree of missingness ².

The DSS Core 2 delivers predictions despite missingness, namely despite the facts that (i) some features may be missing, (ii) the choice of treatment for all data used to train and test the models is random, by nature of the Randomized Clinical Trial, i.e. there is no clinical rationale behind it, and (iii) the evidence needed for validation is missing. We explain these three challenges of learning under missingness and their repercussions on data preparation and validation in **Section 3.1**. The design decisions for dealing with the problem (i) of missing features are in **Section 3.2**. The solution to the problem (ii) on missing rationale is in **Section 3.3**. The solution to the problem (iii) on missing evidence for validation is in **Section 3.4**. The overall performance of the DSS Core 2 is in **Section 3.5**.

¹Choice of three citations:

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- Miro Schleicher, Ruediger Pryss, Johannes Schobel, Winfried Schlee, and Myra Spiliopoulou. Expect the gap: A recommender approach to estimate the absenteeism of self-monitoring mHealth app users. 2022 IEEE 9th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA), 1-10, October 2022

3.1 Learning under Missingness

We explain the three challenges of missingness in **Section 3.1.1**. We outline the data preparation and validation steps in **Sections 3.1.2, 3.1.3**, and list the output of DSS Core 2 in **Section 3.1.3**.

3.1.1 Challenges of Missingness

(i) Missing features: While it is necessary to train the best performing models, the analysis of historical data reveals that different clinics differ in the exact features captured regarding a patient, the exact questionnaires that are collected, the order they are collected in, and that the likelihoods of missingness at the feature- and the questionnaire-level. The DSS Core 2, introduced in this section, has therefore focused on being able to deliver predictions even when some features are missing. The design decisions emanating from the need to learn with missing features (item i) are presented in **Section 3.2**.

(ii) Missing rationale for treatment assignment: In “typical” clinical data, the treatment that a patient receives can be relied upon as the best choice that the clinician could make, given the patient data at baseline. In an RCT, however, the treatment that a patient has been assigned to is random. Therefore, the models in the DSS Core 2 should learn only the degree to which a patient improves given a treatment and in comparison to other patients, and not learn an association between patient characteristics and treatment assignment. We addressed this issue by introducing the concept of 'treatment appropriateness' and conducting the training and validation workflow accordingly, see **Section 3.4.2**.

(iii) Missing verification evidence: Whenever the DSS Core 2 recommends for a patient a different treatment than the one the patient received as part of the randomized treatment assignment procedure, then there are no data to validate the recommendation. We addressed this issue by introducing the concept of 'counterfactual treatment' and conducting the training and validation workflow accordingly, see **Section 3.4.3**.

3.1.2 Data preparation for learning under missingness

The RCT data from all centres were used; no patients were excluded. To ensure that no information were leaked from the test subsample(s) to the training, we performed no scaling and no normalization. The THI score at baseline was excluded (cf. **Section 3.2.1**) because it was found (in preliminary experiments) that it overpowered the predictors.

3.1.3 Output of the DSS Core 2

For each patient, the DSS Core 2 delivers to the front-end one vector per treatment. The vector encompasses (i) the predicted outcome for the treatment, (ii) the confidence of the DSS Core 2 to the prediction, and (iii) the predicted likelihood of adherence to that treatment. DSS Core 2 performs predictions also if some features of the input patient are missing.

3.1.4 Validation of the DSS Core 2

To date, the only population with the same characteristics (in particular: exposure to the RCT treatments) is the UNITI RCT population itself. Hence, validation was done on the same population. Two validation procedures were implemented:

Validation of the DSS Core 2 with respect to prediction quality: This validation concerns the error in predicting the THI improvement (the Δ THI) for each treatment. This was done by holding out 25% of the data; no data were leaked from the validation phase to the learning phase (which encompassed training, testing and hyperparameter optimization). The first intermediate validation appears in **Section 3.3.3** after explaining how we deal with the missing rationale during treatment assignment. The second intermediate validation appears in **Section 3.4.2**, after explaining how we deal with the missing verification evidence. Finally, the overall performance of the ensemble in DSS Core 2 on the heldout validation dataset is in **Section 3.6**.

Validation based on alignment with the RCT: This validation was run under the assumption that the clinician will choose the top-1 treatment in the ranked list delivered by DSS Core 2. Since there are two forms of alignment, we refined the protocol described in the proposal. This validation is described in **Section 3.7**.

3.2 Design Decisions for Learning with Missing Features

The DSS Core 2 concentrates on a ‘core’ set of features that are likely to be recorded for each patient, but can still be missing for some patients; this core set is described in **Section 3.2.1**. The learning algorithm is also chosen to be robust to missingness, as described in **Section 3.2.2**.

3.2.1 Core set of features - single features and aggregate scores

The RCT dataset encompasses a comprehensive array of questionnaires and audiological measurements, positioning it as a valuable resource for future clinical applications. In clinical practice though, it is possible and even likely (as we learned in WP3) that a patient will not fill all the questionnaires. Hence, the features considered for the DSS Core 2 are the following (cf. figure 6), whereby any of them may be missing:

- Single features: gender, age, tinnitus loudness, tinnitus frequency, audiogram,
- Aggregates I: TFI-, WHOQoL-, and Big5- subscales
- Aggregates II: FTQ Score, Mini-TQ Score, GUEF Score, PHQ-9 Score, and
- Tinnitus Severity Questionnaire

Note: the THI Score at baseline was omitted because it overpowers other features.

Figure 6. Patient representation in a high-dimensional feature space encompassing single features, subscales and questionnaire scores

3.2.2 Learning Algorithm that is Robust to Missing Features

XGBoost is a tree-based technique designed to segment data into groups with similar deviations from the group average in a hierarchical manner. It has inherent support for handling missing values, making it versatile for various applications. It exhibits performance comparable to other tree-based methods like Random Forests.

3.3 Solution for Learning and Validation despite the ‘missing rationale’

Our DSS Core 2 solution to the ‘missing rationale’ issue encompasses an adjusted target variable (cf. **Section 3.3.1**), and a method that captures and highlights treatment diversity (cf. **Section 3.3.2**). The results are in **Section 3.3.3**.

3.3.1 Adjusting the target variable

To deal with the fact that the treatments in the UNITI RCT have been assigned to the patients randomly, the DSS Core 2 learns patient improvement in comparison to other patients and thus predicts treatment ‘appropriateness’: instead of predicting for a patient and a treatment the expected ΔTHI , we predict

$$\Delta\text{THI} - \text{average } \Delta\text{THI}$$

where the second term is the average difference in the THI score among all patients who received that treatment during the RCT. We term this adjusted target variable ‘treatment appropriateness’: a treatment is deemed appropriate if a patient’s THI score improves more than the average improvement achieved through random assignment of this treatment.

3.3.2 Learning for diversity: Ensemble of four treatment-level models

To address the diversity among treatments, the DSS Core 2 contains multiple models at treatment-level and an elaborate workflow for learning and validation, which prohibits data

leakage despite the small size of the samples. Since the number of patients per arm was very small, we first estimated the effects of the primary treatments (cf. figure 7), namely of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), Hearing Aid (HA), Structured Counseling (SC), and Sound Therapy (ST) by inducing four models total.

Figure 7. Separate treatment-level models. HA=Hearing Aid, CBT=Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, ST=Sound Therapy, SC=Structured Counselling.

3.3.2.1 How are the four treatment-level models used

The DSS Core 2 allows two ways of prediction with the four treatment-level models:

A model alone: it delivers predictions for the primary treatment it refers to (e.g. ST), whereby it exploits evidence from all arms where this treatment was used (cf. figure 6)

Ensemble-of-four: it delivers predictions for each single treatment and for each pair of treatments, whereupon the vote of each of the four ensemble members is weighted by the member's confidence to its decision

In the present implementation of the DSS front-end, only the ensemble-of-four is used. However, if a clinic wants to concentrate only on some of the treatments, the predictions of the other treatments can be ignored.

3.3.2.2 Sampling for training, testing and validation of the treatment-level models

As per standard procedure for machine learning, the first step in creating the training data for each of the above four models was to create the holdout test set on which all the final models were to be evaluated.

In the DSS Core 2, we held out a stratified sample of 25% of the data for validation, and used the remaining 75% for model learning. The stratified selection ensured that the training data did not over- or under- represent treatments that were observed less frequently than others.

Model learning on the 75% of the data encompassed training, testing and tuning of the XGBoost hyperparameters. This was done by 5-fold cross-validation ³ on these data, *i.e. without touching the holdout dataset that we reserved for validation*. This means that during hyperparameter tuning each model was effectively trained on 60% of the data (4 folds a 15% of the data), and are not exposed to the rest.

3.3.3 Validation of the four treatment-level models on the heldout sample

The target variable, the Δ THI score, is numeric, hence the difference between predicted and true value forms the basis of our evaluation. We chose the Root mean Squared Error (RMSE), *i.e.* we sum the square of the differences over all predictions (for the data in the holdout sample) and compute the square root. RMSE penalizes predictions with large errors. Since XGBoost generates multiple subsets of data hierarchically, the final error is the average RMSE over these subsets. The results of the treatment-level models of DSS Core 2 are depicted on Table 3.

Table 3. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of treatment-level models over the holdout data (25% of the data): An error of 10 units means that a patient who improved by 30 units has a prediction between 20 and 40.

Treatment	CBT	HA	SC	ST
Error: avg RMSE	15.5	14.2	12.6	17.8

3.4 Solution for Validation despite the ‘missing verification evidence’

The predicted improvement for a patient can only be verified for the treatment actually assigned to the patient. But since this assignment was random, the DSS Core 2 delivers also predictions for all other treatments. To deal with the fact that these predictions cannot be verified (cf. **Section 3.1.1.1**), in the DSS Core 2 we introduced a ‘counterfactual treatment evaluation’ method, described hereafter. The sampling procedure for training, testing and validation is the same as described earlier in **Section 3.3.2.2**, but the interpretation of the RMSE is more elaborate, and described under the validation results in **Section 3.4.2**.

3.4.1 ‘Counterfactual treatment’ evaluation method

Core idea of the ‘counterfactual treatment’ evaluation method we designed in DSS Core 2 is that for each patient and each counterfactual treatment, *i.e.* each treatment that the patient did not receive, we compute a counterfactual treatment outcome (the value of the target variable), *i.e.* a counterfactual adjusted Δ THI score, from the data of patients who actually received that

³ The term 'cross-validation' refers to the instrument used to exploit data for both training and testing; this instrument was applied on the 75% of the data reserved for learning. The purpose of cross validation is to maximise the data available for training (over all the folds), while also maximizing the data available for validating the trained models during hyperparameter tuning. The term is not related to the 'validation' we performed on the 25% of the data we held out.

treatment, and use it as verification evidence. The procedure is depicted on figure 8 for the example of a patient who was assigned to the CBT arm during the RCT and whose counterfactual treatment outcome must be computed for the treatment HA.

Figure 8. Computing the outcome of a counterfactual treatment from similar patients who received that treatment: for the given patient (uppermost left corner), the workflow includes (i) identification of similar patients who received the treatment under consideration, here HA, and (ii) computation of the average adjusted DTHI over these patients, while weighting it on similarity to the patient under study, (lowermost right corner of the figure)

The DSS Core 2 method for counterfactual treatment evaluation first identifies the three most similar patients who had actually received treatment HA. It then takes the treatment outcome for each of these three patients, weights it with the similarity to the patient under study, and computes the average of these weighted values.

3.4.2 Validation with ‘counterfactual treatment’ outcomes

The results on counterfactual treatment evaluation are depicted on **Table 4**, again using RMSE (as in **Section 3.4.1**). There is a challenge in the interpretation of these values though:

A low RMSE value does not guarantee that the model is good, but a high error would mean that the model is not to be trusted.

When juxtaposing these RMSE values to the RMSE achieved per treatment by the treatment-level models under verified evidence (cf. Table 3), we see that the counterfactual errors are lower than the errors for the verified evidence, i.e. for the treatment assigned by the UNITI RCT (at random) for all four treatment-level models. This suggests that the models can be

trusted, since the randomization of treatment in the RCT means there is only a 10% chance that the treatment assigned to a patient is the ideal treatment.

Table 4. Root Mean Squared Error for Nearest Counterfactual Neighbor’s Improvement for the four treatment-level models over holdout test data. All errors are lower than the predictions over actual ground truth, suggesting that the models can be trusted. As in Table 3, the error is the average RMSE over all the subsets of the validation data automatically generated by XGBoost

Counterfactual Treatment Evaluation	CBT	HA	SC	ST
Error as avgRMSE	10.4	12.9	11.5	12.0

3.5 Additional developments since the submission of the 1st D5.2 version

Several models were trained and compared, including a neighbourhood-based predictor at treatment level. Neighbourhood-based predictors were chosen because they can be implemented in such a way as to tolerate missing features. The RMSE achieved on the validation dataset was ca. 19 units, hence the XGBoost-based approach was upheld.

The XGBoost-based learner was extended to predict the adherence likelihood for each treatment. Four additional treatment-level XGBoost-based predictors were developed that concentrate on improving the outcome at the 5th and 95th quantile.

3.6 Performance of the final version of the DSS Core 2

The DSS Core 2 delivers for each patient the predicted outcome per treatment, even if there are features missing in the input patient’s record (cf. Section 3.2). To deal with the problem of ‘missing rationale’ for treatment assignment in the RCT, it uses our adjusted Δ THI score and predicts with the ensemble-of-four (cf. Section 3.3). To deal with the ‘missing verification evidence’ issue, it validates predictions with our ‘counterfactual treatment’ evaluation method (cf. Section 3.4). The overall RMSE of DSS Core 2 on the adjusted Δ THI score is 15.87.

The RMSE per treatment is depicted in the table below, whereby the prediction for each pair of treatments (TreatmentX + TreatmentY) comes from two of the four treatment-level models, hence two RMSE values are delivered. The values are cut at the second position after the comma.

Table 5. Root Mean Squared Error from the ensemble-of-four treatment-level predictors: for each single treatment, only one treatment-level predictor delivers predictions, hence one RMSE value is computed; for each pair of treatments, two of the treatment-level predictors deliver predictions, hence two RMSE values are computed.

RMSE when predicting the improvement for treatment	RMSE of the Treatment-level predictors			
	CBT-predictor	HA-predictor	SC-predictor	ST-predictor
HA		12.86		
HA+CBT	7.3	6.48		
HA+SC		5.46	4.29	
HA+ST		9.11		13.03
ST				16.62
SC			8.51	
CBT	11.79			
SC+CBT	11.19		14.72	
ST+SC			13.54	12.30
ST+CBT	15.51			12.24

Notes on the interpretation of this table:

1. The ensemble of treatment-level predictor does not predict the best treatment but the expected improvement for each treatment.
2. For the predictor validation on a specific treatment or combination, we consider only those patients in the validation subsample that actually received this specific treatment. For some arms, the number of such patients in the validation subsample is very small, hence some RMSEs are less reliable. In general, this is more likely for treatments that have many dropouts and for patients that were involving hearing aids, since not all RCT participants were eligible for them.

3.7 Validation of DSS Core 2 according to the alignment protocol of the UNITI proposal

The originally planned validation protocol disagrees with the design of the DSS: the DSS Cores do not choose among the treatments but rather return (for presentation to the clinician) the predicted Δ THI together with the confidence of the model in the prediction. To perform the validation, we aligned the RCT arms with the DSS Core 2 as follows: for each patient, we ranked the treatments on the Δ THI predicted by the DSS Core 2, and we selected the top-1,

i.e. the one with the largest improvement in the THI score. This corresponds to assuming that the clinician would choose the treatment with the largest predicted Δ THI.

3.7.1 Two types of alignment

- Binary alignment: the treatment arm of the RCT is the same as the top-1 treatment in the ranked list of the DSS Core 2 (alignment = TRUE) or is not (alignment = FALSE).
- Ternary alignment: the treatment arm of the RCT contains one treatment component that is also contained in the the top-1 treatment of the DSS Core 2 (alignment = 1) or contains no common component (alignment = 0) or consists of two components that are both identical (alignment = 2).

Example: patient x was assigned to the RCT arm 'CBT'; for this patient the top-1 treatment in the ranked list of DSS Core 2 is 'CBT+SC'. Under binary alignment, the alignment value is FALSE. Under ternary alignment, the alignment value is 1.

3.7.2 Quantities measured

For each value of alignment, we present and compare (a) the THI score after treatment, where smaller values are better; (b) the Δ THI, i.e., the 'THI improvement' and (c) the percentage change in THI with respect to baseline, i.e., the THI improvement percentage. For each of these indicators we return the average value (in a table), the density and the population distribution.

3.7.3 Validation Set

For the validation of the predictions done by the DSS Core 2, we used the heldout validation set, cf. **Sections 3.3.3, 3.4.2, 3.6**. For the alignment with the RCT, we used the complete dataset of the RCT. This guarantees that we have adequate data for each treatment (aligned and not aligned) to acquire reliable results.

To ensure that no unfair advantage is allotted to the DSS Core 2, we checked the likelihood of alignment in the heldout dataset vs complete dataset. If the DSS Core 2 were overfit, then it would have predicted with high likelihood the treatment that the patient actually received and the THI improvement that the patient actually experienced, whereupon the alignment would be disproportionally high (i.e. close to 100%) among the training data. This is not the case: the percentage of aligned patients is 24.4% in the heldout dataset and 27.7% in the complete dataset.

Hence, for the validation on alignment, we used the complete dataset. It contains **376** patients.

3.7.4 Results for binary alignment

Table 6 below contains the average THI score, THI improvement and percentage thereof for the 272 patients that were not aligned and the 104 patients that were aligned.

Table 6. Average THI scores for the groups with and without alignment

Alignment	THI Score	THI Improvement	THI Improvement Percentage	N (count)
FALSE	38.91	10.09	19.6%	272
TRUE	23.60	22.60	45.8%	104

Figure 9. Visualization of the binary alignment. The three stacked figures depict the value distribution (upper subfigures) and percentage of population (lower subfigures) of THI scores (leftmost subfigures), THI improvement (middle subfigures) and percentage thereof (rightmost subfigures). The prefix 'Binary_' refers to the binary alignment. It is noted that in the upper subfigures, the blue curve is always higher than the orange one, reflecting the fact that there are more non-aligned patients (more than 2.5 times as many) than aligned ones.

For the THI score, the orange density curve is more shifted to the left than the blue one, i.e. towards smaller THI scores (smaller is better). The orange population curve is also more shifted to the left, indicating that more of the aligned patients exhibit a smaller THI score than is the case for the non-aligned patients.

For the THI improvement and for the percentage thereof, the orange density curves are more shifted to the right than the blue curves, indicating that the improvement among the aligned patients is larger (larger is better). The orange population curves are accordingly shifted more to the right, towards the larger (better) values.

Statistical testing:

Welch's t-test was applied to compare the means of aligned and non-aligned patients for THI score, THI improvement and percentage thereof. The null hypothesis that the means are the same is rejected in all cases. The p-values shown below are before Bonferroni correction, but obviously remain significant after correcting for multiple testing (three tests).

Table 7. Statistical results for the tree comparisons.

	statistic	p-value	df
THI Score	7.70	3.51E-13	240.74
THI Improvement	6.54	6.71E-10	172.84
THI Improvement Percentage	8.45	3.00E-15	235.18

Focusing on patients with THI improvement of more than 7 units:

In UNITI, a THI score improvement of more than 7 units is considered 'significant'. Among the non-aligned patients, only 57.7% experienced such an improvement, in contrast to 83% of the aligned patients.

Conclusion for binary alignment:

These results indicate that when the treatment assigned to a patient by the RCT was the same as the one predicted by the DSS Core 2, then this treatment was also the best choice for the patients, and it has lead with higher likelihood (83% vs 57.7%) to 'significant improvement' of the THI score.

3.7.5 Results for binary alignment

The table below contains the average THI score, THI improvement and percentage thereof for the 272 patients that were not aligned and the 104 patients that were aligned.

Table 8. Average THI scores for the groups with and with different levels of alignment

Alignment	THI Score	THI Improvement	THI Improvement Percentage	N (count)
0 (no alignment)	41.98	7.63	14.27%	167
1 (partial align.)	34.04	14.00	28.20%	105
2 (full align.)	23.60	22.60	45.84%	104

The average THI score is ca. 10 units lower for patients with full alignment than for patients with partial alignment; for non-aligned patients it is 7 units higher than for partially aligned ones.

The differences in the improvement values are more drastic: the average improvement among partially aligned patients is twice as large as for non-aligned ones; for fully aligned patients, it is thrice as large.

Figure 10: The three stacked figures depict the value distribution (upper subfigures) and percentage of population (lower subfigures) of THI scores (leftmost subfigures), THI improvement (middle subfigures) and percentage thereof (rightmost subfigures). The prefix 'Ternary_' refers to the ternary alignment.

The tendencies observed under binary alignment are also observed here: The density curve for the set of patients with full alignment are shifted towards the better values (smaller THI scores, larger THI improvements).

Focusing on patients with THI improvement of more than 7 units (minimal clinically important difference for the THI):

The likelihood of significant improvement was 53.89% among the non-aligned patients, in contrast to 63.81% among the patients with partial alignment, and in contrast to 83.65% of fully aligned patients.

Statistical testing:

Tukey's HSD test for equality of means over multiple treatments was applied to compare the means at the different levels of alignment. According to the test, the means between 0-overlap and 1-overlap case is different with $p=3.62E-03$; the means between 0-overlap and 2-overlap is different with $p=6.71E-13$; and the means between 1-overlap and 2-overlap is different with $p=2.80E-4$

Table 9. Statistical results for the tree levels of alignment. Test statistics and p-values of Tukey's HSD test are shown for all contrasts (test statistic; p-value)

	0 (no overlap)	1 (partial overlap)	2 (full overlap)
0 (no overlap)	0; 1	-6.37; 3.62E-03	-14.97; 6.71E-13
1 (partial overlap)		0; 1	-8.60; 2.80E-04
2 (full overlap)			0; 1

Conclusion for ternary alignment:

These results indicate that when the treatment assigned to a patient by the RCT was fully aligned to the one predicted by the DSS Core 2, then this treatment was also the best choice for the patients, and it has led with higher likelihood to 'significant improvement' of the THI score. Patients with partial alignment also experienced more improvement than non-aligned patients though less than non-aligned patients.

4 Notes on sustainability, deployment, and release of the DSS beyond UNITI

Both DSS cores have been made available over a Flask API to ensure easy integration into current and future systems. The current outputs of the two DSS cores are integrated into the Tinnitus Database front-end where the physicians can not only view the patient data, but also see the predicted improvement for the patient given each of the ten combination therapies. The two DSS core outputs are shown side by side, and the final determination of the most applicable treatment is left to the physician's discretion. This conservative approach is necessary since a complete validation of the treatments in a clinical environment is outside the scope of UNITI, as it needs a further trial where the DSS recommendation (treatment with lowest final THI) is followed, and the predicted post-treatment THI is validated outside an RCT environment.

5 Conclusion

The DSS is a pivotal element of the tinnitus-database.eu ecosystem, bridging advanced analytics with clinical expertise. It stands as a paragon of innovation in healthcare technology, providing a foundation for personalized treatment strategies that cater to the unique needs of each tinnitus patient. As it integrates seamlessly into clinical workflows, the DSS is set to redefine the standards of patient-centered care in tinnitus management.